

Variety	Damage rating ^a												
	IRRI						Bangladesh		Solomon Islands		Sri Lanka		
	Biotype 1		Biotype 2		Biotype 3		SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST	
	SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST							
Sinna Sivappu	1.5 a	1.0 a	1.5 a	1.5 a	1.0 a	1.5 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	5.5 a	6.0 a
Kencana	6.5 bc	2.5 ab	6.0 c	1.5 a	6.0 bcd	3.0 ab	9.0 c	9.0 c	7.8 bc	6.8 de	7.5 bc	6.0 a	6.0 a
IR26	3.0 a	2.5 ab	8.5 d	8.5 c	3.5 ab	4.0 ab	8.0 c	5.0 b	8.8 c	7.0 e	7.0 ab	8.0 b	8.0 b
IR46	1.5 a	1.5 ab	8.0 d	1.5 a	4.0 bc	3.5 ab	6.0 b	5.0 b	7.0 b	3.0 b	7.5 bc	8.0 b	8.0 b
ASD7	2.0 a	1.0 a	3.5 b	1.5 a	8.5 d	8.5 c	9.0 c	9.0 c	7.5 bc	5.5 c	8.0 bc	8.5 b	8.5 b
Utri Rajapan	6.0 b	2.0 ab	7.5 cd	1.0 a	6.5 cd	4.5 ab	9.0 c	6.0 c	9.0 c	6.0 cd	7.5 bc	5.0 a	5.0 a
Triveni	8.0 cd	3.0 b	8.5 d	5.0 b	7.5 d	6.5 bc	9.0 c	6.0 c	8.0 bc	7.2 e	7.0 ab	5.5 a	5.5 a
TN1	9.0 d	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 c	8.0 d	9.0 c	9.0 c	9.0 c	9.0 c	9.0 f	9.0 c	8.5 b	8.5 b

^a By the SES scale 0–9: 0 = no damage, 9 = plants killed. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

(SSST) to identify field-resistant varieties in the greenhouse. Varieties in which resistance is expressed in older plants are useful because their resistance may be stable and not easily broken down by the selection of virulent biotypes.

The feeding behavior of the South Asia BPH population differs from that of Southeast Asia BPH. Some varieties that are resistant in Southeast Asia are not resistant in South Asia and vice versa. A collaborative project compared the SSST and the modified standard seedbox screening test (MSST) in tests conducted in the Philippines, Bangladesh, Solomon Islands, and Sri Lanka. Seeds of eight varieties and methods for conducting the tests were sent from IRRI. Varieties were selected on the basis of their reactions in SSST and in IRRI fields.

Sinna Sivappu was the resistant (R) check, TN1 was the susceptible (S) check. IR26 was selected as the basis for testing IR46. IR26 is S to biotype 2 in the SSST and in the field; IR46 is S in the SSST but R in the field. ASD7 is a R check for biotypes 1 and 2 and a S check for biotype 3. Kencana, Utri Rajapan, and Triveni are S in the SSST, but moderately R to R in the field.

Test insects were reared on 60- to 80-d-old TN1 plants except for biotypes 2 and 3, which were reared on Mudgo and ASD7 at IRRI.

In the commonly used SSST, 25 seeds of each variety are sown in a 60- × 45- × 7-cm seedbox in 20-cm rows with

5-cm spacing between rows. Varieties are arranged in a randomized complete block design with one row of each variety replicated four times. At 7 d after sowing (DAS), each seedling is infested with 8 to 10 2d- or 3d-instar nymphs. When plants in the S TN1 check are killed, damage is scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

The design and methods used for MSST are the same as for SSST except that each seedling was infested at 10 DAS with 3 to 5 2d- or 3d-instar nymphs. The F₁ progeny of the initially infested insects killed the S check about 28 d after initial infestation.

Kencana was moderately susceptible (MS) or S to all three biotypes in the SSST in all countries, but R in the MSST at IRRI (see table). IR46 and IR26, with the same major resistance gene (*Bph 1*), had similar reactions in the SSST at all locations. In the MSST, however, IR46 was R to biotype 2 and

the Solomon Islands population, IR26 was S. In IRRI field tests, IR46 was R to biotype 2.

Utri Rajapan and Triveni had lower damage ratings in the MSST than in the SSST at all locations. At IRRI, Utri Rajapan had a rating of 7.5 in the SSST and 1 in the MSST for biotype 2. It becomes tolerant of biotype 2 after the seedling stage in both greenhouse and field tests.

Only Utri Rajapan and Triveni showed field resistance across all locations. The lack of uniformity in Kencana and IR46 may be due to a lack of field resistance to certain populations or to some variation in the methodology used.

Utri Rajapan is being used as a donor of field resistance to BPH in breeding programs at IRRI. It also has a high tolerance for BPH and whitebacked planthopper and is resistant to rice tungro virus. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization COLD TOLERANCE

Variability in yield and yield components of normal and late-sown rice in West Bengal

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Stagnant rainwater or flash floods in Jul

and early Aug often damage the seedbed or newly transplanted seedlings. Farmers have to prepare fresh seedbed. When floodwater recedes, new seedbeds cause late transplanting in the main field.

Varieties adapted to different sowing times are needed to replace traditional

Variability in yield and yield components under normal and late sowings. Malda, West Bengal, India, 1985-86.

Sowing date	Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Sterility (%)
13 Jul	CN657-21	106	161	21	8	120	28	2.5	19
	CN671-28	111	149	24	7	173	25	2.8	18
	CN671-29	102	131	23	10	145	30	2.6	20
	Mean	106	147	23	8	146	27.6	2.6	19
10 Aug	CN657-21	92	137	23	11	122	29	1.5	19
	CN671-28	101	121	23	9	127	28	1.5	23
	CN671-29	87	98	22	13	103	29	1.8	24
	Mean	93	119	23	11	117	28.6	1.6	22
	% reduction	12.3	19.0	0.0	-37.5	19.8	-3.6	38.46	
<i>F</i> value ^a	Variety (V)	180.4**	81.05**	0.07 ns	6.83**	130.5**	34.4**	0.84 ns	
	Sowing (S)	635.2**	39.23**	0.014 ns	12.61**	303.6**	9.4**	6.55**	
	V × S	11.9**	1.3 ns	0.019 ns	0.46 ns	95.72**	19.1**	0.34 ns	

^a ** = significant at the 1% level.

varieties.

Late-planted rice generally encounters two environmental factors that can reduce yield: a gradual decline in average night/day temperatures and drought during the reproductive stage. The effects are pronounced in northern West Bengal.

We conducted an experiment in the old Gangetic alluvium region at Malda (25°33'N) to identify important characters for late sowing and to evaluate the effect of temperature on the reproductive stage.

Three advanced lines derived from CNL 231/Pankaj and Pankalash/CRI006 crosses were sown on 13 Jul and 10 Aug. The 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted 20 × 15 cm apart in 5-m² plots with 5 replications. Fertilizer was applied 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha.

In the variability study, heading duration, total grains/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight significantly differed among varieties and by sowing date, and variety × sowing interaction (see table). Although plant height, filled

grains/panicle, and yield were reduced by 19, 19.8, and 38.5% in late sown rices, effective tiller numbers and 1,000-grain weight increased.

Days to heading was 102-111 in the Jul-sown crop and 87-101 in the Aug-sown crop. Average temperature was 26.5°C during panicle initiation for Jul and 23.3°C for Aug sowings. Average temperatures of 22°C and 20°C prevailed during grain filling.

Although low temperatures were not critical for mid-Aug sowing, sterility % was higher with late sowing. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Drought tolerance of some rice hybrids and their parents

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In several crop plants, hybrids have shown higher drought tolerance than their parents. This has been attributed to deeper and more developed root systems. Under such situations as midseason rain failures in rainfed rice, this capacity could make the difference between a relatively good crop and a total failure.

We evaluated 11 rice hybrids and their parents for drought tolerance in a split-plot design in 2 replications using 15 plants each during the 1984 dry season. Irrigation treatments were in main plots and the hybrids and their parents in subplots. Irrigation was withheld for 14 d at late tillering or panicle initiation. Plots were normally irrigated afterwards. The mean values and percent reduction of four traits under normal irrigation and under drought stress are presented in the table.

Grain yield reduction in five hybrids was less than in the lesser affected parent. In another five hybrids, it was between the two parents. Only one hybrid had higher yield reduction than

both parents, probably because this hybrid flowered in late May and was affected by hot winds.

Among the parents, Taichung Senyu 285 had exceptionally high tolerance for drought, with higher yield under stress than all the other hybrids. None of the correlation coefficients between characters were significant. □

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